

Figure S1: Alignment of all linkage groups markers to *F. varia* genome assembly (F_var1.2).

BLAST results show synteny between linkage groups to genome scaffolds. Some markers placed at the same position in the linkage map but returned hit to different scaffolds have denoted as an extra line. A marker without a BLAST hit points towards white space. Local ordering of some scaffolds shows hits more than once at some locations, denoted by an asterisk(*). Some scaffolds matched to more than one linkage group, and they have been highlighted with light blue text color and a hashtag superscript (#) for better visualization. Blue boxes are drawn to represent the matching genome scaffolds, but their size is only an approximate indicator of scaffold size.

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